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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF POST-DISCHARGE CARE CONTRIBUTES
TO THE DISEASE CONTROL OF PATIENTS WITH COPD****Dr Mahnoor Nasir¹, Dr Hammad Amin Mirza², Dr Umair Sarfraz³**¹Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi, ²Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Medical University,
³Islamabad Medical and Dental College.**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract**

Introduction: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a preventable and treatable disease that is characterized by airflow limitation.

Objectives: The main objective of the study is to evaluate the post-discharge care which contributes to the disease control of patients with COPD.

Material and methods: This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi during January 2019 to July 2019. The data was included from those patients who hospitalized, aged 18 years or more, and diagnosed with COPD.

Results: The data was collected from 120 patients of COPD. The data was divided into two groups one was intervention group and one was control group. The mean age of the patients was 52.24±6.11 years. After intervention the symptom score in the extended care group (52.53±2.84) was decreased compared with the usual care group (67.26±3.78), which indicated that the extended care contributed to control the clinical symptoms of patients with COPD (P<0.05).

Conclusion: It is concluded that a comprehensive response to the needs of severely affected COPD patients with acute exacerbations can only be achieved through models of shared care utilising all relevant health providers in efforts to treat the exacerbation and also prevent readmission.

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a preventable and treatable disease that is characterized by airflow limitation. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is usually progressive and associated with an enhanced chronic inflammatory response in the airways and the lungs to noxious particles or gases. Exacerbations and comorbidities are known to contribute to the overall severity in individual patients [1]. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease remains as a major public health problem worldwide. By 2020, it is projected that COPD will rank fifth globally in burden of diseases, according to a study published by the World Bank/World Health Organization [2].

Depending on the stage of COPD, the illness will have a significant impact on the life of patients. Patients have to cope with physical symptoms such as breathlessness, reduced activity level and malnutrition. Patients often report isolation, loss of independence, reduced quality of life and depression [3]. Additionally, COPD often coexists with other diseases that may have a significant impact on the prognosis. During the last 15 to 20 years, the development towards better treatment, rehabilitation, care and medication has taken massive steps forward, and the attitude towards this group of patients has changed: "a nihilistic attitude towards the patient with COPD is no longer justified". Instead, patients with COPD nowadays meet with well-informed⁴, multidisciplinary and intersectional teams work together with the patient with the goal of helping and educating him/her to self-management, stable physical condition and to increase quality of life, as recommended by global initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) [5].

Many of these initiatives are based on the chronic care model (CMM) as defined by Wagner. The six components of this model are: organization of health care, self-management support, decision support, delivery system design, clinical information system, community resources and policies. The essential purpose of the model is to increase the quality of health care without increasing cost. The main issue is the patient-centered approach and then the model recommends systematic care planning, intersectional collaboration, patient empowerment, evidence-based care, and ongoing evaluation of humanistic, clinical and economic outcomes [6].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the post-discharge care which contributes to the disease control of patients with COPD.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi during January 2019 to July 2019. The data was included from those patients who hospitalized, aged 18 years or more, and diagnosed with COPD. According to the patient's discharge order, the patients were alternately assigned to the observation group and the control group and received different care measurements. The length of observation is 3 months. We determined the classification of COPD according to the GOLD as follows: 1) GOLD-2 of COPD, the FEV₁ expected value is $\geq 50\%$, but $< 80\%$; 2) GOLD-3 of COPD, the FEV₁ expected value is $\geq 30\%$, but $< 50\%$; and 3) GOLD-4, the FEV₁ expected value is $< 30\%$. Extended care includes the following measures: health guidance, helping to quit smoking, guiding medication, respiratory exercise, physical training, long-term home oxygen therapy, psychological care, family visits, social support and nutritional support.

We used the St George's respiratory questionnaire (SGRQ) to evaluate the subjective efficacy. SGRQ mainly includes 50 evaluation items, which can be divided into three items to measure as follows: activity ability, clinical symptoms and the impact degree of COPD to daily life.

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 120 patients of COPD. The data was divided into two groups one was intervention group and one was control group. The mean age of the patients was 52.24 ± 6.11 years. After intervention the symptom score in the extended care group (52.53 ± 2.84) was decreased compared with the usual care group (67.26 ± 3.78), which indicated that the extended care contributed to control the clinical symptoms of patients with COPD ($P < 0.05$)

Table 01: Clinical information and general data of the included patients (140 cases)

Items	Classification	Group A	Group B
Gender	Male	40 (57.1)	40 (83.9)
	Female	30 (42.9)	10 (17.1)
Smoking	Yes	43 (61.4)	39 (55.7)
	No	27 (38.6)	31 (44.3)
Education level	Primary	34 (34.3)	26 (37.1)
	Middle	28 (40)	24 (34.3)
	University and above	18 (25.7)	20 (28.6)
Monthly economic income	<10,000 RMB	18 (25.7)	22 (31.4)
	≥10,000 and ≤15,000 RMB	28 (40)	24 (34.3)
	>15,000 RMB	24 (34.3)	24 (34.3)

Table 02: Comparison of pulmonary function between groups (M ± SD)

Group	Intervention	Group A	Group B	T-value	P-value
FEV ₁ % (M ± SD)	Before intervention	0.36±0.16	0.35±0.19	0.31	>0.05
	After intervention	0.51±0.15	0.55±0.09	5.34	<0.05
FVC% (M ± SD)	Before intervention	0.41±0.13	0.49±0.13	0.42	>0.05
	After intervention	0.50±0.12	0.51±0.13	7.56	<0.05
FEV ₁ /FVC (M ± SD)	Before intervention	0.59±0.14	0.59±0.16	0.80	>0.05
	After intervention	0.60±0.13	0.71±0.14 ^c	8.91	<0.05

DISCUSSION:

Qualitative data suggested that health professionals valued bundles as a means of focusing on standardised quality of care, but staff lacked experience and knowledge in QI strategies. This reflects the findings of Lennox *et al*, who identify the barriers and facilitators to care bundle implementation⁷. As other authors have identified, the local context, governance structures and financial incentives for support were crucial in determining whether, and how effectively, sites implemented care bundles. We observed the use of discharge ‘checklists’ at comparator sites, which often represented ‘bundling by another name’. As a result, similar processes and activities seemed to be taking place at implementation and comparator sites. This is likely to have reduced the ability of the study to demonstrate difference in outcomes attributable to care bundles^[8].

To achieve improvements in outcomes, care bundles must meet three criteria: the target outcome must be sensitive to change and responsive to the elements within the bundle; the care bundles must be reliably implemented to ensure that the majority of patients receive bundle-led care; and use of the care bundle must improve process reliability ^[9].

In this study the bundles were not delivered reliably, with delivery of the full five-item admission bundle and discharge bundle being very low, although there is some evidence from our data that those patients in receipt of a bundle received more of the required elements of care, suggesting some improvement in process reliability ^[10]. The third criterion was not met since most patients did not receive the full set of bundle elements. Therefore, effective implementation of the admission and discharge bundles did not occur and the anticipated difference between groups was not observed ^[11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that a comprehensive response to the needs of severely affected COPD patients with acute exacerbations can only be achieved through models of shared care utilising all relevant health providers in efforts to treat the exacerbation and also prevent readmission. Extended care improves the quality of life of patients with COPD after discharge, which is conducive to the rehabilitation of respiratory function and the psychological health of patients.

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